

NOTES ON THE VELVET SPIDER *GANDANAMENO FUMOSA* (C. L. KOCH, 1837) FROM SOUTHERN AFRICA (ARANEAE: ERESIDAE)

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Abstract: The large velvet spiders of the African genus *Gandanameno* Lehtinen, 1967 are known from five species. One of the species, the tree velvet spider *Gandanameno fumosa* (C.L. Koch, 1837) is known from South Africa and now also from Namibia. The species was observed over a period of 18 months. This paper reports on their web building and feeding behaviour, distribution and conservation status.

Key words: behaviour, predation, taxonomy, distribution, conservation

INTRODUCTION

The Eresidae in southern Africa is represented by five genera (Dippenaar-Schoeman *et al.* 2020). Three genera, *Paradonea* Lawrence, 1968 (Miller *et al.* 2012), *Seothyra* Purcell, 1903 (Dippenaar-Schoeman 1991) and *Stegodyphus* Simon, 1873 (Kraus & Kraus 1988) have been revised and information is available on their distribution and lifestyle. However, the genera *Dresserus* Simon, 1876 and *Gandanameno* Lehtinen, 1967 are less known and in need of revisions.

The velvet spiders *Gandanameno* and *Dresserus* resemble each other in general appearance and shape. They both share a peculiar modification of the median spinnerets. However, they differ in the cribellum of *Dresserus* being 4-partite, having a secondary septum in both plates, compared to the 2-partite of *Gandanameno*. In the males, *Dresserus* can be distinguished by having two horn-like tubercles on the antero-lateral border of the carapace.

It is frequently difficult to distinguish between *Dresserus* and *Gandanameno* species only from photographs. Based on the combination of genetic, morphometric, and spinulation data, Miller *et al.* (2012) saw no evidence that the characters traditionally used to discriminate *Gandanameno* species are valid. They speculated that ontogenetic factors may be responsible for the morphological variation observed in species of this genus. However, they decided that the synonymy of all *Gandanameno* species would be premature, particularly in light of the phylogeographic signal suggested by the molecular data.

As part of the South African National Survey of Arachnida (SANSa) large numbers of specimens were sampled (Dippenaar-Schoeman *et al.* 2015, 2020), including several eresid genera such as *Gandanameno*. The genus *Gandanameno* is currently known from five species. One has been reported from Malawi, but the other four all originate from southern Africa (World Spider Catalog 2020). Of these, three species were described from South Africa and one from Namibia.

During SANSa, several species of *Gandanameno* were identified, including the tree velvet spider *Gandanameno fumosa* (C.L. Koch, 1837). The female of *G. fumosa* was described by as *Eresus fumosus*, with the type locality only given as “Africa” (C.L. Koch 1837). Tucker (1920) described the male

for the first time, based on a specimen from Naauwpoort, near Hanover in the Northern Cape. *Gandanameno fumosa* was assessed for the IUCN Red List (Foord *et al.* 2020).

The first author (AE) collected a male and female eresid in Namibia and sent it to the second author (ASD) for identification. The specimens were identified as *G. fumosa*. This represents the first confirmed record of this species from Namibia. Specimens were observed over a period of 18 months in Namibia, and in this paper we provide information on the behaviour, distribution and conservation status of *G. fumosa* in southern Africa.

MATERIAL AND METHODS

Study area: The first author observed *Gandanameno* activity on the farms Vergenoeg (21°11.53'S, 18°18.34'E) and Otjitambi in the Outjo district of Namibia over a period of 18 months. The spider activity was documented and specimens were photographed.

Voucher specimens: A male and female from Namibia have been deposited as voucher specimens in the National Collection of Arachnida (NCA 2020/554) at the Agricultural Research Council in Pretoria. Specimens sampled during the SANSa surveys are also housed in the National Collection of Arachnida (NCA).

Photographs: All the photographs were taken by the first author.

RESULTS

Species morphology: *Gandanameno fumosa* is a large spider with a velvety appearance. It is very closely allied to *E. echinatus* (Purcell, 1908), a species known from Namibia, the only differences being the spinous integument of the sternum and parts of the legs. In *E. fumosus*, the sternum is thickly covered with minute sharp spinules distributed between the setae, the coxae of the two anterior legs, and the third coxa are also more densely spinulose. The patellae of the two anterior pairs of legs are covered in dense but very short spinules on the anterior side. It shares with *G. purcelli* (Tucker, 1920) the white spotted abdomen, but differs by the more densely spinulose areas.

Description: Female (Figs 1 & 3): body size: 23–25 mm. Carapace rectangular; dark-brown, almost black, slightly darker in cephalic region; cephalic region strongly raised, densely clothed with setae; fovea circular; eyes eight, median eyes close together, with lateral eyes wide apart and posterior lateral eyes usually positioned far back on the carapace. Abdomen oval and densely clothed with setae; dark grey with short setae that form small white spots and faint chevron markings; white setae form white rings around dorsal sigilla; cribellum 2-partite. Legs same colour as carapace; stout and thickly clothed with setae; tarsi and metatarsi usually united by almost rigid joints; coxae and femora I and II densely spinulose (Fig. 6). Sternum thickly covered with minute, sharp spinules. Epigyne with copulatory openings that are broadly separated by hirsute cuticle (Fig. 5).

Male (Figs 2 & 3): smaller in size, 9-10 mm. Carapace dark-brown, almost black; slightly arched posterior to fovea, thus leaving a more level, fan-shaped area on each side from fovea to border; surface finely granular and covered in white setae; thoracic portion broader than cephalic region, also covered in white setae. Abdomen infuscated testaceous, slightly darker on under surface and sparsely covered with short whitish hairs and longer darker ones; dorsal sigilla white-ringed, and posterior to sigilla are 4-5 light oblique markings sloping down from central line. Sternum dark brown. Legs same colour as carapace; covered with pale hairs with a whitish sheen. Juveniles differ from adults in colour and the abdomen lacks a spotted appearance (Fig. 4).

Global distribution: In Southern Africa the species is recorded from five provinces in South Africa and Namibia.

Conservation measures: The species is sampled from the Fynbos, Savanna, Desert and Succulent Karoo biomes (Foord et al. 2011). Presently it is protected in the Polokwane Nature Reserve (Dippenaar et al. 2008); Richtersveld Transfrontier National Park (Dippenaar-Schoeman 2020b); Tswalu Game Reserve (Dippenaar-Schoeman et al. 2018); Goukamma Nature Reserve and Table Mountain National Park (Dippenaar-Schoeman 2020c). There are no significant threats to the species, and due to its wide geographical range, it is listed as Least Concern.

Figure 1. *Gandanameno fumosa* female from Namibia.

Figure 2. *Gandanameno fumosa* male from Namibia (Photo: A. Eichhoff).

Figure 3. *Gandanameno fumosa* small male (left) and female (right).

Figure 4. *Gandanameno fumosa* juvenile.

Figure 5. Epigyne NCA 2020/554.

Figure 6. Leg spinules (From Miller et al. 2012).

Retreat web: The retreat of *G. fumosa* is frequently made in holes and openings in the rough bark of trees such as *Vachellia luederitzii* (Kalahari thorn) (Fig. 7). The retreat is usually made in the bottom third of the trees. It was also observed attached to rough boulders, with the retreat in a slit in the boulders. The retreat of the female consists of three parts: the flat catch web, anchor lines and the tunnel retreat.

The sheet-like catch web resembles a flat mosque tent. It is made of white cribellated silk. The size of the catch web (Fig. 10) varies depending on the size of the inhabitant; one measured 10 x 10 cm. The catch web is anchored to the substrate with numerous strong anchor lines (Figs 8 & 9). The catch web covers and opens into the retreat area, which consists of a number of tunnels. The size and number of tunnels depends on the age of the female.

The spider takes up position at the tunnel entrance with her front legs on the catch web, waiting for prey (Figs 10 & 11). This was seen during the day and at night. A female that caught a weevil pulled the insect into the tunnel before she started feeding.

Different insects have been identified from remnants left in the web, such as beetles, termites and ants (Fig. 12).

Figure 7. *Gandanameno fumosa* retreat.

Figure 8. *Gandanameno fumosa* showing the anchor lines.

Figure 9. *Gandanameno fumosa* showing the anchor line attachments (marked in yellow).

Figure 10. *Gandanameno fumosa* showing the catch web.

Figure 11. *Gandanameno fumosa* on the catch web.

Figure 12. Prey remains on the catch web.

In a *Ficus* tree a large nest was observed, consisting of dry leaves and silk (Fig. 13). When the nest was opened, ten different spiders were sampled, consisting of a female, an immature male and eight juveniles (Fig. 14). The egg sacs are deposited in the mother's nest (Fig. 15).

The male has his own retreat, about 30 X 15 mm in size, close to the female's nest. When the female dies her family seems to stay in close affinity, making their own webs close by (Fig. 16).

Figure 13. *Gandanameno fumosa* nest in tree.

Figure 14. Inhabitants of the nest . Figure 15. Egg sac in mother's nest .

Figure 16. Young spider new retreats close to the mother's nest..

CONCLUSION

Little is still known about the behaviour of many spiders, especially species of rare genera such as *Gandanameno*. This is the first record of the behaviour of *G. fumosa* in southern Africa. We now know they are active at night and make a catch web, feeding on a variety of insects. Juveniles tend to stay in close affinity to the female before building their own retreats close by.

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